

INDIGENOUS KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICES OF THE AGTA COMMUNITY AND THEIR ROLE ON ENVIRONMENTAL GOVERNANCE AT SITIO MALIKON-LIKON, BARANGAY SAN JOSE, SAN MARIANO, ISABELA

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ABSTRACT

The Agtas' indigenous knowledge and practices (IKP) possess traditional systems, beliefs, and values that have been transmitted through generations. It is known to have an invaluable IKP, which contributed to the sustainable management of natural resources in their ancestral domain. The purpose of this study was to determine whether Agtas' IKPs have a role in environmental governance. This study will also look at co-management efforts and the problems faced by the community and the local government agency pertaining to the environment and natural resources. The study conducted key informant interviews and in-depth semi-structured interviews with respondents who had first-hand knowledge about the community. The findings of the study revealed a clashing perspective from the key respondents, especially between the Agta and the LGU. The Agta considered themselves as among the protectors and guardians of nature. They believe that their IKPs play an important role in managing the environment as they provide skillful actions regarding resource use and conservation management. While the LGU recognizes this knowledge and practices of the Agta, findings show that their only contribution is to report illegal activities and that the Agtas' IKPs are not that inclined to the environment and natural resources mission. The LGU emphasized that the culture of the Agta is more geared toward utilization, so they do not rely much on the Agta when it comes to governing the environment. Contrary to various research claims that the IKP of the indigenous people has a substantial role in environmental governance, it reveals recognition of the Agtas' IKPs but little effort to include the Agta community in the overall governance of the environment. The study concluded that the Agtas' IKPs contributed to the management of the environment, yet there is still a discussion as to whether their IKPs are suitable for this changing time.

Keywords: *Indigenous knowledge and practices, Agta people, environmental governance, IKPs*

INTRODUCTION

San Jose is a barangay in the municipality of San Mariano, in the province of Isabela. Its population, as determined by the 2020 Census, was 2,622. This represented 4.36% of the total population of San Mariano. The Agta people who live at Sitio Malikon-likon in Brgy. San Jose, San Mariano, has a rich cultural heritage that includes indigenous knowledge and practices, specifically in the preservation of the environment. Indigenous Knowledge and Practices (IKP) is defined as an extensive and valuable knowledge system that is adaptable and dynamic, based on skills and abilities that change over time depending on environmental conditions. IKP concerning nature includes knowledge, practices, and representations developed by communities by interacting with the natural environment and learned behavior that is influenced by modern times. With their sustainable knowledge and practice which helps in the preservation of the environment, evidence shows that indigenous peoples are among the most effective stewards of the environment (Rasmussen, 2023). Despite a pool of research that supported that IPs together with their IKP have been proven to contribute to the sustainability and productivity of many ecosystems, their IKP, to which their survival and cultural identity revolve largely, there has been undeniably a noticeable deterioration of their IKP (Philippine Resource Center for Sustainable Development and Indigenous Knowledge, 1998).

The general purpose of the study is to determine the involvement of the Agta community in environmental governance. In particular, the researchers sought to answer the following research questions: (1) What are the

indigenous knowledge and practices of the Agta community? (2) How do the indigenous knowledge and practices affect the role of the Agta community in environmental governance? (3) How do the Agtas' indigenous knowledge and practices contribute to their local decision-making concerning environmental problems? (4) How do the Local Government Unit of San Mariano and the Agta community foster co-management efforts on environmental governance? (5) What are the challenges faced by the Agta community and the Local Government Unit of San Mariano in dealing with environmental governance?

METHODS

The qualitative method was used for this study. The data needed for the study was obtained by the researchers through Key Informant Interviews (KII) as primary data and secondary data provided by the office of the NCIP. The KII is a qualitative, in-depth interview with people who have first-hand knowledge about the community.

The study was conducted at Sitio Malikon-likon, Barangay San Jose, San Mariano, Isabela. The Agta, the Local Government Unit (LGU), specifically the Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office (MENRO) of San Mariano, Isabela, the National Commission on Indigenous Peoples (NCIP) of San Mariano, Isabela and the Community Environment and Natural Resources Office (CENRO) of District II, Isabela, collaborated in this study.

The study used a semi-structured interview guide. The researchers conducted interviews with the respondents using two (2) sets of formulated semi-structured interview guides that assisted the generated data. One for the Agta and one for the LGU-San Mariano. The researchers identified eight (8) respondents. One (1) Agta leader and five (5) elders, two (2) individuals from LGU, specifically the MENRO and CENRO.

The researchers used thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is a method of analyzing qualitative data. It is usually applied to a set of texts, such as an interview or transcripts. The researchers transcribed the permitted audio record and analyzed it to draw useful conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Agta's Indigenous Knowledge and Practices (IKP)

The Agta has a rich cultural heritage that includes traditional hunting, fishing, rattan gathering, honey collection, and forest conservation. The Agtas' IKPs are presented in the following areas: forest land, inland waters, and wildlife are discussed.

Agta's IKP on Forest Land

The Agta has various IKPs pertaining to the environment. Their IKP is deeply tied to their sustainable relationship with the environment, guiding the preservation and proper use of natural resources. The Agtas' IKP on forest land is discussed below.

a. Rattan Gathering

One of the Agtas' practices is rattan gathering. The Agta Ancestral Domain Sustainable Development Protection Plan (ADSDPP) provides data for rattan gathering, which is one of the Agtas' practices. The Agta practices the spreading of widely matured rattan fruits under the tree cover, which preserves them in turn. According to the ADSDPP (2019), the Agta gather rattan only for domestic purposes, such as building their belay (house), and is used in tying their harvests, such as fish and meat of wild pigs. Today, the Agta gathers rattan poles all throughout the year to sell or trade since rattan crafts are in demand. This data implies that as time goes by, the Agtas' IKPs are adaptive to changing times.

b. Honey Collection

According to ADSDPP (2019), the Agta has a rich knowledge of detecting the location of wild beehives or kalabe through taladog, a process of looking at the sun to find the direction of abundant bees. The taladog process is said to be taught to the Agta boys at an early age, which serves as a challenge since it is not easy to collect honey. The ADSDPP provides data for this technique of collecting honey. Accordingly, to collect honey, the use of a torch of about four (4) feet in length and three (3) feet in diameter is made of *sakon* leaves tied with vines. The torch is said to be lit until it emits smoke, and the smoke is said to drive away the bees in their beehives, and that is their cue to cut the beehive using a bolo and put it in a container called *luwit*. This is supported by the study

of Aldovino et al. (2013), where the Aeta of Quezon Province smokes cigarettes when gathering honey from the *ligwan*. The smoke draws away the *ligwan* from the combs. Thus, it is much easier to cut and collect the combs.

c. *Use of bolo and stick*

According to Mr. Kamuning, “*kapag kami ay nagtatanim, bulo at stick na sariling gawa ang gamit namin, upang sa gayon hindi... kasi diba ngayon puro de makina na, hindi iyon maganda para sa lupa*” (when we are farming, we use only bolo and stick which we makes... today, machineries are widely used, so it is not good for the soil). Accordingly, Mr. Kamuning stated, “*ang topsoil kasi... nandodoon lahat ng sustansya at pataba, kung ito ay gagamitan mo ng mga makina, eh hindi ito kagandahan... sa pag gamit ng bulo at stick, napapanatili nito ang kalidad ng topsoil*” (the natural nutrients and fertilizer is in the topsoil, and so if it uses machineries, it is not that good... so by using a bolo and a stick, it will maintains the quality of the soil).

d. *Use of stalks of corn and rice straw*

Mr. Kamuning added, “*kung nakikita nyo, yung mga tangkay ng mais ay iniwan lang namin at hinahayaan na ito ay mabulok at kung kami ay nakikisaka sa baba, yung dayami ay hinahayaan lang din namin dahil ito ay nagsisilbing likas na pataba sa lupa*” (if you see, we just leave the stalks of corn and let it rot and if we labor at the lowland, we also leave the rice straw because it serves as a natural fertilizer for the soil).

This is similar to the study of Naganag (2013), where the farms in Tanudan are always drained with water to facilitate the composting of the rice stalks from the previous crop and to make the soil soft and humus. This is called the practice of *dosdos*, and they use their feet to stomp the soil until it turns muddy. The rice stalks from the previous crop are pushed with the use of their feet to the ground. This will, in turn, serve as a natural fertilizer when rotten.

e. *Butngol and talinga ti kahoy*

Furthermore, the Agta believed that the spirits inhabit trees that are found in the forest. In connection to this, one of the Agtas' IKPs as communicating to their environment. The Philippines is a tropical country and currently experiencing heat waves and high temperatures. According to Mr. Kamuning, “*ngayong sobrang init, may kasanayan kami na ginagamit namin sa pagpapa-ulan at pagpapahinto ng ulan. Ito ay ang butngol at talinga ti kahoy na galing sa punong kahoy*” (now that we are experiencing a heat wave, we have a practice where we could make it rain and stop. This is the *butngol* and *talinga ti kahoy* that is acquired from a wood).

Mr. Kamuning explains that when the excessive heat cannot handle the forest cover, they practice their knowledge in rain-making rituals. This practice uses *butngol* and *talinga ti kahoy*, which is the *butngol* is a wood acquired from a tree, as well as the *talinga ti kahoy*, which is a wood ear-shaped, which is also acquired from a tree. The process of the rain-making ritual includes a female and male *butngol* that must form a whole. While it is moved up and down to the river, incantations are said and after two days, the rain will come. The process of calming the rain is using *talinga ti kahoy*, which is a wood ear-shaped that is set on fire, and after a while, the rain stops.

Agta's IKP on Inland Waters and Fishing

Inland waters are a basic natural resource of the Agta. It has a variety of fish and clams. Their ancestral domain is rich in water resources like creeks, rivers, and streams. This is where they do all things such as bathing, washing dishes and clothes. The stream is their main source of water for drinking and cooking, and so it is kept clean from waste. The ADSDPP provides data for this practice of sanitation of water bodies. Accordingly, it is their traditional way of disposing of their bodily wastes where they practice dumping and cover dig holes away from the rivers, creeks and springs so they will have a clean source of potable water.

a. *Use of weeds*

The usual practice of the Agta on inland waters is gathering fish. Most of the respondents said that they do not practice destructive fishing. In fishing, Mr. Kamuning said, “*kasi kami hindi naman kami gumagamit ng dinamita at kuryente*” (we don't use dynamite and practice electrofishing). Mr. Kamuning elaborated that they have been practicing a safe fishing tool that uses weeds (*sikal*) that they often throw to identify the location of the fish. Accordingly, he stated, “*sa pamamaraang ito, hindi nasisira ang ilog*” (in this method, the river will not be damaged). The Agta believed that this safe practice contributes largely to taking care of the natural environment, ensuring that natural habitats and fish stocks are safeguarded and maintained.

b. *Use of sigay*

According to Mrs. Talisay, “*may sinusunod kami sa pangingsda, hindi basta basta, depende sa laki*” (we follow selective fishing, it’s not random, we catch fish depending on its size). The Agta practice selective fishing as they catch only those fit for consumption. Accordingly, Mrs. Talisay stated, “*gumagamit kami ng sigay upang siluin at mahuli ng mas mabilis [ang isda]*” (we use nets to easily trap and catch the fishes). In gathering resources in inland waters, the Agta believed that the condition of the fish must be observed when fishing. Pregnant fishes, young ones, and extinct types of fishes were left alone to let the fishes reproduce and multiply.

c. *Use of bettek and antipara*

The ADSDPP provides data for these fishing tools that are used by the Agta to gather fish in the rivers. The *bettek* is a wooden spear that has a metal point that is used to catch the fish, and the *antipara* is a self-made goggle that is used together to catch various fish. These fishing tools are made indigenously by them. This is supported by Hagen et al. (2017), a study conducted in the same municipality, where three (3) Agta settlements are found using the same traditional fishing tools. Self-made goggles (*antipara*) which are used to catch various types of fish, metal spears around 50cm in length (*bakal*), and a larger spear, either made completely out of metal or in the form of a metal point placed on a wooden spear (*battik*), is used to catch giant mottled eel.

Agta’s IKP on Hunting

The Agtas have been practicing sustainable hunting and provide knowledge of when and what to hunt.

a. *Selective Hunting*

Most of the respondents claimed that they are mindful of what to hunt. According to Mrs. Malabulak, “*yung masakog na hayop, tsaka bata at mga mababangis na hayop na malapit na mawala ay hindi na namin hinuhuli*” (Pregnant animals, younger ones and those wild animals that are endemic are left alone). This selective hunting allows endemic animals to multiply first, the same practice in gathering fish, which helps to conserve the wildlife in the forest. This kind of practice will help wildlife maintain and sustain their homes, balancing biodiversity in which diverse ecosystems thrive just as people do.

b. *Hunting techniques and tools*

It is said that the Agta are known for their traditional hunting practices and that the learning process in hunting techniques starts at an early age. In traditional hunting, the Agta uses a bow and arrow as a tool to hunt. The tip of the arrow is made through a large flat stone called *pandayan*. Accordingly, the Agta has four (4) techniques in hunting: the *manganop*, which is used in hunting wild pigs and uses bow and arrow with the guidance of a pet dog; the *mangalidop*, which also includes the use of bow and arrow but without the guidance of a pet dog; the *bellatik* or using spear trap and *sekwat* which uses snares. The spear trap is a wood with a metal spear at its peak, a trap that is set up to kill large animals. *Sekwat* is a hunting technique that is a circle-shaped trap designed to injure animals that walk through the circle.

c. *Seasonal hunting*

Furthermore, Mrs. Intsia said, “*may sinusunod kaming buwan sa panghuhuli...*” (we practice seasonal hunting). This is true of what the NCIP recorded in the ADSDPP, which stated that Agta strictly followed the time frame during which it was allowed to hunt animal species. In their ADSDPP, from May to August, the Agta and non-Agta are not allowed to hunt and kill because this is the time when animal species reproduce.

The Agtas’ IKP in hunting contributes largely to the proper use of resources found in the wildlife while benefiting it and allowing wildlife to reproduce so as to lessen the extinction of ecosystem species. Generally, they practice the *Gaygay* System, which literally means fencing a certain area that prohibits the entrance of anybody. Accordingly, the *gaygay* is done by tying red cloth in the area that they need to protect, such as protecting trees and fish in the rivers and protecting the resources from depletion for a certain period of time. It is obvious that the Agta community has deep connections to the environment— land and waters and its resources, which possesses a rich knowledge and practices that have sustained them for generations. Evidently, their knowledge and practices have been sustained and substantially used throughout generations. However, as modernity, intermarriages, and mainstream education systems dominated, this greatly led to the disintegration of the Agtas’ cultural values. The IKP is slowly diminishing because the parents failed to transfer it to their children

(ADSDPP, 2019).

Effect of IKP to the Agta's role on Environmental Governance

All of the respondents said, as Mr. Kamuning stated, "*kami ang nakatira rito, kaya't alam namin pangalagaan ito*" (we live here, so we know how to take proper care of our place). When the researchers interviewed and asked the LGU-MENRO whether the Agtas' IKP affected the role of the Agta on environmental governance, the LGU-MENRO stated, "The only role of the Agta is to report illegal activities done by the lowlanders." While the DENR-CENRO said, "They serve as forest guards." Thus, findings revealed that Agta's IKP determined their role in environmental governance as being the forest guard and reporter of illegal activities that occurred in their ancestral domain.

Contribution of Agta's IKP to Local Decision-making on Environmental Problems

The Agta believe that, as a protector of the environment, their role contributes to nature preservation, as they lived in the area a long time ago and know the behavior of the forest. Mr. Kamuning said, "*kung may problema man, alam namin solusyunan ito*" (when there is a problem, we know how to deal with it). When the researchers asked the DENR-CENRO whether the Agtas' IKP has a contribution to local decision-making concerning environmental problems, the DENR-CENRO said, "We seek their expertise when there is a problem at the site of the project, which is the National Greening Program (NGP) but aside from that, we do not include the community because the decision-making process is internal."

The findings of the study revealed that DENR-CENRO sought the Agtas' expertise when a project collaborated by both of them had encountered problems and as to combating environmental problems, the decision-making as to how it will be resolved is internal and within the agency.

Co-management efforts of Agta, LGU-MENRO, and DENR-CENRO on Environmental Governance

a. National Greening Program (NGP)

One of the present and annual projects of the DENR-CENRO is the NGP, which envisions conducting massive forest rehabilitation. When the NGP is introduced to the Agta, according to Mr. Kamuning, "*sila talaga ay nagpapaalam, dalawang araw na may pag uusap at mga katanungan, nung nagustuhan namin ang proyekto, pinayagan ko kasi ito ay para sa ikabubuhay din ng mga kasama ko... maganda naman...*" (ever since they really let us know if they will enter our domain, for two days, discussions and questions about the project were held and when we liked the project, I agreed because the intention was good and it was also for the livelihood of my tribe). Since the project weighs more positively, the Agtas commit to fostering cooperation and co-management within the project, and the DENR-CENRO acknowledges Agta as one of its implementers of the said project. The DENR-CENRO stated, "Since the project is within the ancestral domain, we tap the Agta because they are well-versed, and they thrive in the forest."

b. Northern Sierra Madre Natural Park Conservation Project

The LGU-MENRO, on the other hand, said that its first and last project that involved the Agta was the Northern Sierra Madre Natural Park Conservation Project, which happened way back in the 1990s. Although the project happened ages ago, there has been continuous cooperation since Agta was regarded as one of the forest guards and reporters of illegal activities. The LGU-MENRO stated, "We are not closing the door for future collaboration with the Agta."

Problems faced by the Agta, LGU-MENRO, and DENR-CENRO in dealing with Environmental Governance

a. Unsupervised Kaingin

According to Mrs. Agoho, "*hindi maalam sa kaingin po ma'am ang isa sa problema na nakikita ko*" (the practice of unsupervised kaingin ma'am, is one of the problems I observed). Kaingin is widely perceived as one of the biggest problems in various research studies, as supported by Persoon et al. (2020), which states that this practice is often described negatively and is considered a form of using resources that is wasteful and inefficient. Continuous practice and not being mindful of kaingin will lead to soil erosion and eventually to the destruction of the forest.

b. *Activities done in the protected area without permit*

According to Mrs. Banaba, “*maliban sa pagpunta ng ibang lahi dito na kumukuha ng mga punong kahoy at nagpuputol na walang permit ay wala na...*” (except for the presence of migrants who conducts activities such as cutting of trees and extracting woods that don't have permits, we don't have any [problem]).

The office of NCIP said that activities such as logging and extracting natural resources are not limited to Agta only but also for everyone. Accordingly, it is said that natural resources are for everyone, and in order to conduct activities such as logging and kaingin, one needs to have a permit given by the DENR to ensure that the activity was done through the right process and monitored.

c. *Agtas as one who conducts activities without permit*

On the other hand, one of the problems that the LGU-MENRO and DENR-CENRO faced is that the Agta, who should be at the forefront of protecting the environment, are also one of the illegal loggers. Some were timber coaching and practicing kaingin, which resulted in land spills in the forest zone. Timber coaching is an act of providing comprehensive knowledge to others who are foreign to the area, allowing certain information to reach foreign actors. The LGU-MENRO emphasizes that these activities, such as logging and kaingin, are not legal unless it has a permit and abide by environmental laws.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, findings revealed that despite useful IKPs, which provide proper use of natural resources, LGU-MENRO and DENR-CENRO emphasized that they do not rely much on the Agtas when it comes to the preservation of the environment because the Agta's culture is more of utilization. Accordingly, there are knowledge and practices that are no longer suitable, so they adapt to the modernization that is introduced to them in order to survive. Gradually, due to the influence of lowlanders, some of the Agtas' IKPs are kept integral to their culture, but not all are practiced.

Despite a pool of research that shows that the Agtas' IKPs and their role have been recognized, the Agtas' IKPs are still finding their seat in environmental governance.

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